

EVENT REPORT

Business Principles for the Stakeholder Capitalism Era

NOVEMBER 29-30, 2022 | ONLINE & IN BRUSSELS

On November 29-30, 2022 ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society convened its 21st Annual Colloquium during which speakers and participants engaged in keynote speeches, panel discussions and interactive sessions on the timely topic of "Business principles for the stakeholder capitalism era". The event took place online on November 29 and in hybrid format on November 30.

Academics, progressive businesses and international organizations like ABIS have been calling for an "expanded" role of business in society for decades.

In this year's Colloquium, we aimed to move beyond specificities and fragmented approaches towards a **holistic understanding of responsible business conduct** in light of the evolving concept of **stakeholder capitalism**. Albeit not new, this concept has been reforming the way we think about business and advocating for a system in which businesses are oriented to serve the interests of all their stakeholders. The main outcome of the event was a **set of principles** serving as guideposts for business in the stakeholder capitalism era.

Audience

The Colloquium welcomed managers, practitioners and business and management scholars who want to enhance business competitiveness as well as social and environmental sustainability in a world in transition towards more inclusive, stakeholder and regenerative models. We were glad to:

- have **over 100 registrations**
- from which we welcomed **75 participants** at the online and offline event
- representing **53 organizations...** and **20 countries!**

If you missed the event, you can now find **session summaries, available recordings** and **resources for further learning** below.

Day 1: Opening remarks and Panel Discussion on "Managing Business in the Stakeholder Capitalism era"

After a welcome speech by Karolina Sobczak, Knowledge Manager at ABIS, and opening remarks by **Baback Yazdani**, Chair of the Board of Directors, ABIS and Executive Dean, Nottingham Business School, the official program started with a panel discussion among

- **Luca Condosta** - VP HR - Leadership Learning Ecosystem Community lead, ABB
- **Crispen Sachikonye** - CEO, Social Value UK
- **Lisa Gring-Pemle** - Associate Professor of Business and Co-Executive Director, Business for a Better World Center, George Mason University
- Moderator: **Karolina Sobczak** - Knowledge Manager, ABIS

Lisa Gring-Pemle opened the panel linking the emergence of stakeholder capitalism to the **need to solve big problems which are interconnected** across disciplines, geographies and cultures. These are encapsulated by the SDGs and many businesses are recognizing their role in addressing them. The success of the private sector is in fact tied to social justice, stakeholders, equity, humanity, and society and it depends on education and leadership. Part of this responsibility lies on business schools, that need to adapt.

Crispen Sachikonye explained how [Social Value UK](#) both contributes to and challenges stakeholder capitalism. They prepare organisations to become more responsible, by challenging the view of focusing on what is material to the organisations themselves. They propose to refocus on the benefit or harm stakeholders actually experience as a result of an organization's activity, following 8 principles, including: **involving stakeholders**, so that they can inform what gets measured and done; focusing on **valuing all the things that matter** (above and beyond dividends); considering **materiality**, i.e. how stakeholders are impacted by what has and has not been done and **decision-making** (i.e. are organizational decisions responsive to stakeholder needs?).

Bringing the business perspective, **Luca Condosta** highlighted the concept of **extended enterprise**: companies need to be considered as a piece of the system. Changing the way they operate, the whole system changes accordingly. Materiality should indeed not be about risk management, but about the company's role within the system. Only when considering multiple and diverse stakeholder perspectives the company can materialise its impact in the short and long term.

Not taking stakeholder interests into consideration can jeopardize companies' survival. Companies not updating their business models will become obsolete!

A lively discussion among the panellist and audience followed. Key insights were:

- **societal challenges are business issues**, and businesses increasingly recognize that they are better off taking care of such challenges (regardless of how their efforts are labelled)
- we live in a world where language can shape behaviours and beliefs and concepts such as ESG and stakeholder capitalism are shaping the narrative of how we talk about businesses. In this process, it is hard to avoid green or pink washing and corporate action might not be perfect, but overall **the narrative is shifting, there is movement towards change**
- building on the theory of signals, the more leaders and society are educated to recognize certain signals, the lower the probability of greenwashing taking over and the higher the probability of actual change in operations and policies. This calls for **sustainability literacy and education**, which must be provided not only by business schools, but also by primary and secondary education institutions as well as internally by companies
- the [Doing Good Model](#), inspired by values-based leadership and implemented by a number of companies including Cisco, and Liverpool John Moores University's adoption of the principles of Social Value were mentioned as **best practices** creating positive social value; ABB's engineering focus on producing the best motors to save energy is also an example of **embedded sustainability** (practiced without being even claimed) vs sustainability as an add-on. Several companies are taking the same approach and stakeholder capitalism can help bring out these practices and cases to the surface
- criticism related to materiality and trade-offs among stakeholder needs can be addressed by moving away from quantitative thinking and perfectionism to **becoming comfortable with uncertainty and ambiguity, together with transparency** about decisions taken and the underlying reasons, which creates accountability as well as learning and improvement cycles; it is also important to ask more questions about decision-making and impact and to increase corporate awareness about their power to generate positive impact
- the **importance of humanities education** was also pointed out as leaders are increasingly required to understand the historical context and the socio-political and economic factors that shape corporate action and to ask questions about purpose, ethics, justice, democracy and responsibility in the business context e.g. *are we really valuing the things that matter?*

- a game changer will also be **democratization of leadership** and the idea that everybody is a leader as it is up to each of us how much power we want to use as consumers, as employees and as decision-makers in our daily choice; there is a need to train and upskill leaders as they are often used to grow to gain power rather than to use the power and skills they already have to manage externalities and generate relevant, positive impact
- the future of for-profit business and "doing good" are not mutually exclusive. It is possible to find a place in the middle, sustainable and valuable both for society and for businesses, with the narrative around profit potentially shifting from dollar signs to value delivered

Imagine a business making decisions armed with tools not only from finance, accounting and marketing, but also a sense of their context, daring questions, creativity, ethics and measurement of things that are hard to measure?

ACCESS THE RECORDING HERE

Day 1: Latest research findings

In this session, academic experts and practitioners from the ABIS network and beyond presented latest research findings and cases at the crossroads of sustainability strategy, business model innovation and stakeholder capitalism. Most of the findings will be published in an upcoming Special Issue of the Emerald Corporate Governance Journal.

The following pages provide an overview of the research and cases presented in 6 themed tracks:

- 1.1 Leveraging corporate governance and the role of boards
- 2.1 Stakeholder capitalism: challenges and limits
- 3.1 Value creation and stakeholder engagement approaches
- 1.2 Exploring leadership and ethical perspectives
- 2.2 Spotlighting specific stakeholder groups
- 3.2 Adopting stakeholder-oriented business practices and models

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Adopted					
Revised					
Amended					
Deleted					
Added					

Recording...

Lara Gianina Reyes

Track 1.1 Leveraging corporate governance and the role of boards

- Chair: **Josep Pinyol**, ABIS
- **Habeeb Yahya**, Turku School of Economics: *CEO/Board characteristics: Examining the role of women in the sustainability performance of firms*
- **Hans Taparria & Bruce Buchanan**, New York University, Stern School of Business: *Community Governed Capitalism: Using the Butterfly Charter*
- **Lara Gianina Reyes**, University of the Philippines Los Baños: *Overcoming Conformance Inertia: Pushing Philippine Boards towards Stakeholder Value Creation*

RECORDING

Changing the perspective to change the dynamic: Placing the community at the center of stakeholder theory

John McArdle, Associate Professor, Bertolon School of Business, Salem State University, Salem, Massachusetts, United States

Alice de Koning, Teaching Professor, Haskayne School of Business, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada

Track 2.1 Stakeholder capitalism: challenges and limits

- Chair: **Maury Peiperl**, George Mason University
- **Kyoko Sakuma**, Solvay Brussels School of Economics and Management & **Dirk Coeckelbergh**: *How the Belgian ethical bank NewB failed to cultivate steward investors*
- **John McArdle**, Salem State University: *Stakeholder theory development*
- **Duane Windsor**, Rice University: *Integrating three theories of capitalism*
- **Ferran Curtó & Eloi Gummà**, ESADE: *Focusing on the capitalist side of the equation: an assessment of stakeholder capitalism as a suitable business paradigm-shift*

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Purpose of Research

Research Question

What is the stakeholder's engagement process in public projects?

Aim

Examine stakeholder's engagement process in public projects.

Objective 1

Explore current engagement process success/failure

Objective 2

Identify barriers (institutional/context)

Objective 3

Identify ways of integrating stakeholders into social value creation

Objective 4

Develop a framework for stakeholders engagement

Draw implications of research to theory /practice

Track 3.1 Value creation and stakeholder engagement approaches

- Chair: **Kosheek Sewchurran**, University of Cape Town Graduate School of Business
- **Christiane Molina**, Tecnologico de Monterrey: *Purpose-driven stakeholder engagement: a case-study of value co-creation in textile artisans' communities*
- **Cynthia Akwei**, Liverpool John Moores University: *Integrating Stakeholder's Engagement Strategy in Existing and New Social Value Strategy in Developing Economies*
- **Rashed Hasan**, George Mason University: *The Stakeholder Value Creation Index: A Partnership Between Business and Higher Education*

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Track 1.2: Exploring leadership and ethical perspectives

- Chair: **Kosheek Sewchurran**, University of Cape Town Graduate School of Business
- **Walter Baets**, Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences: A system's view on leadership: from 'me' to 'we'
- **Rob Price**, Alchemmy & **Jessica Huntingford**, Resolvo: Corporate Digital Responsibility – From the International Manifesto to the Micro-enterprise -
- **Adaeze Okoye**, University of Brighton: African 'igwebuike' business ethical philosophies and sustainable stakeholder capitalism

RECORDING

Values based leadership: An upfront choice for the system

Our prevailing thinking is Cartesian
(choice for 'me' and the 'ratio')

Our leadership theories are control driven, the leader and the followers, leadership 'qualities', targets

Monetarist liberal capitalism (1980s)

Focus on competition

We don't even try to 'measure' stakeholder value

versus

Ubuntu (Desmond Tutu): I am because we are
I am since I belong

Responsibility
Reliability
Respect
Reconciliation
Recognition

Making the Invisible Visible: Stakeholder Capitalism and Powerless Stakeholders

Harry Van Buren
University of Tennessee at Chattanooga

Judith Schrempf-Stirling
University of Geneva

Track 2.2 Spotighting specific stakeholder groups

- Chair: **Josep Pinyol**, ABIS
- **Derrick Chong**, Royal Holloway University of London:
Contemporary artists as activist stakeholders
- **Harry J. Van Buren**, University of Tennessee: *Making the Invisible Visible: Stakeholder Capitalism and Powerless Stakeholders*
- **Karina Ochis**, Monarch Business School Switzerland:
Prioritizing Young Employees Under Stakeholder Capitalism

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Track 3.2 Adopting stakeholder-oriented business practices and models

- Chair: **Maury Peiperl**, George Mason University
- **Jan Beyne**, Antwerp Management School: *How can materiality assessments be used to define sustainability priorities, while taking into account the SDGs?*
- **Marcia Lorena Rodríguez-Aldana, Lilia Patricia López Vázquez, Lucía Alejandra Rodríguez Aceves**, Tecnológico de Monterrey: *Exploring the impact of conscious business on reputational capital of SMEs*
- **Gregory Unruh**, George Mason University: *Implementing the Doing Good Model: The Arison Group and George Mason University Bridge the Business and Educational Divide*

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Day 2: Introduction and keynote speeches

The second day was introduced by **Manuela Brusoni** who, as a member of the Colloquium Steering Committee, outlined the underpinnings of the principles-based stakeholder approach of the event. This represents a **mindful and reflective alternative** to the overwhelming production of models, criteria, and prescriptions in the sustainability field. She suggested the route of a **circular stakeholder approach**, in which different elements of corporate value creation (e.g. fulfilment of market needs, shareholder return or relationships with suppliers) could be cyclically assessed with respect to how they sustain each other. Professor Brusoni also brought up the possibility of applying **Archimede's principle as foundation for stakeholder value creation**, alluding that: *"Any organization immersed in a fluid, liquid society is buoyed up by a force equal to the weight of the fluid displaced by the*

organization". The net force on the organization would be the difference between the magnitude of the lifting effect and the weight of societal constituencies. If this net force was positive (i.e. the organization was deeply engaged in creating value for all stakeholders), the organization would rise; if negative, the organization would sink.

Corporate keynote speech: Business performance that matters

Pauline Bieringa, Managing Director at **Triodos Bank**, started her keynote speech by sharing some takeaways from the first day of the event, highlighting the positive atmosphere despite the current political circumstances. Among the others, she pointed out the paradigm shift towards **community as the center of purpose-based corporate action** and the need to move beyond net-zero to transformation and regeneration. There is a movement for behavioural change that is already happening and education is key for this change.

Ms Bieringa compared her previous banking experience with Triodos' focus on social impact, balancing risks and returns of the projects that they finance. Triodos was founded in 1980, but a crucial time was the 2008 financial crisis that exposed flaws in the banking industry. There was and there is a **need to finance change, but also to change finance**. By providing only services that make profit compatible with sustainability, Triodos plays a role as frontrunner and positive activist and aims to collaborate with other institutions. For instance, the bank does not provide consumer credit to counteract consumerism and has founded the

[Global Alliance for Banking on Values](#), a network of banks using finance to deliver sustainable development. Triodos cooperates with the EU and European Investment Fund and aims to become CO2-neutral by 2035. In doing so, Triodos demonstrates that it is possible for banks to be a force for good.

Reflecting the importance of the community that Triodos has created, a distinguishing feature that was illustrated by the speaker was the bank's **capital structure**. Triodos does not have traditional shareholders, but certificate holders who have delegated their rights to an administration office. This structure protects the bank from being taken over by speculative buyers, as the value of certificates is determined internally independently from external circumstances. More recently, the bank started issuing green bonds.

Triodos is a bank, but actually we are a community with a banking licence. This gives a better idea of our mission.

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Lastly, Ms Bieringa touched upon the dilemmas of a value-based bank, for example the issue of financing only dark green projects or the transition to such projects as well. In their efforts to change finance, they are also experiencing increased competition, which forces them to look for new market areas, such as bio-based mortgages. Another issue is the retention of co-workers, as other banks try to recruit employees at Triodos to build their own sustainable practices. Increasing the visibility of Triodos efforts, retaining the community feeling with their clients and working together with likeminded companies and academia were mentioned as ways to tackle these challenges.

Academic keynote speech: The power of AND - Implementing stakeholder capitalism

Professor Freeman wrote a paper in the 70s, before his 1984 book [“Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach”](#), reflecting on what would happen if stakeholders would be taken seriously. The paper had scarce impact initially, but over time, people started paying more attention and the story of business – what it is and what it can do - is really changing.

Until recently, business was defined as making money for shareholders, ideally in a context of unregulated markets, in which people only care about self-interest. The 2008 financial crisis sparked the perfect storm to induce change in this story. It led to increasing awareness of social issues such as inequality, poverty, racism, gender discrimination and global warming. At the same time, we have witnessed the re-emergence of terrorism and wars, the fracturing of states and a global pandemic. **No one can seriously argue that the way out of this poly-crisis is focusing on shareholder value.** The objectives of business are changing towards sustainability, CSR and environment, society and governance (ESG). New ideas and calls for reform are emerging, e.g. inclusive and conscious capitalism, corporate contributions to the SDGs and socially responsible investing (e.g. the work of [JUST CAPITAL](#)). Against this backdrop, Professor Freeman has questioned the need to label or to choose one best approach/brand in favour of understanding a few key elements that need to shift, which are summarized in his latest book: [The Power of AND](#). The book sparked debate and gained critiques both from the left and the right.

In Freeman’s view, stakeholder capitalism is about what it takes to successfully run a business in today’s world. One of the five ideas in the book is **Purpose and profits**

and debunks the false dilemma between the two. Profit is a necessary element for businesses, but it is not the only driver that motivates businesses. Making profits is compatible with working for a purpose - indeed, most entrepreneurs are motivated by passion and purpose around a societally useful idea. A second idea is **Shareholders and Stakeholders**. The latter are not necessarily at odds with the former. Any business throughout time has created (or destroyed) value for both and a key mindset shift is realizing that shareholders and stakeholder go together. Although we are used to think in terms of trade-offs, these interests are interconnected and interdependent. Exploring the interdependence and harmonizing stakeholder interests is necessary for business to succeed. The third idea relates to **Societal Issues and Market Forces**: thinking of business as a merely market institution unaffected by societal issues is outdated. This is linked to the fact that human beings are not only economic maximisers and are often driven by other values and emotions. The new narrative of business must take into account our complex **Humanity and our Economic Interests**. Lastly, the fifth idea combines **Business and Ethics** together. Business has played a great role – positive and negative - in the emergence of our society and ethical business conduct is needed to contribute to a future worth leaving to generations to come.

In essence, **stakeholder capitalism is about how business model has to change** and there is considerable evidence of this change already happening. These reflections have also implications on the role of business schools. Economics, finance and accounting have dominated at the expense of other disciplines, such as humanities. Future students need to learn business with new perspectives and a more holistic vision of business and society.

Interactive session

In the last session of the event, our participants engaged in an interactive discussion reflecting on the key takeaways, trends, areas of uncertainty and emerging responsibilities for corporate action. The main outcome was a preliminary set of principles that could serve as guideposts for business in the stakeholder capitalism era. The inputs to the question “*Outline key principles for business to follow in the stakeholder capitalism era*” received from participants during the registration phase were first presented. Next, the audience engaged in a series of brainstorming conversations in groups, which results were reported to the plenary. A final selection of principles was shared in the form of a word cloud.

The most impactful principles to drive responsible business conduct identified were:

- **Stewardship:** taking responsibility for the effects the business has on the world around it
- **Shared value** (building on Porter & Kramer's concept): caring about customers, employees, communities and the environment that they operate in, harvesting what they seed!
- **Humanity:** demonstrating values of integrity, benevolence and care for others and future generations (*being able to look loved one in the eyes and feel good about it*) as well as welcoming human emotions
- **People, essence and core:** people ought to be at the core of any organizational activity
- **Double materiality:** accounting for how economic, environmental, or social factors affect the financial value of a firm, and how the firm affects the environment and society
- **Long-term viability:** thinking strategically about long term value (even if intangible) over short term profits
- **Systemic perspective/Holisticness:** developing awareness of the broader environment a company operates in and that the value it creates (or destroys) is not just financial
- **Reputation:** creating value and doing good can enhance corporate reputation and protect companies from the effects of bad reputation

- **Impact, risk, return:** navigating the impact made, the risks taken and for which return
- **Openness and inclusion:** being open and transparent towards customers and communities, including the feedback that comes back in business decisions and being engaged in societally relevant conversations
- **Connectivity:** creating and exploring connections between people and different kinds of stakeholders, leveraging digital technologies
- **Ethical decision-making:** taking ethics into consideration when making business decisions
- **Talent-centred business:** considering current and future staff as key resource and valuing them and their talent
- **Fair value for fair value chain:** embracing equality and fair trade in a more radical way, paying everyone properly across the value chain
- **Fair profit:** aligning profit with purpose and broadening the concept of profit to include the value to the ecosystem and its priorities
- **Circular economy:** changing production (and consumption) patterns and embracing the 4Rs - reduce, reuse, recycle and remove
- **Harmonizing 3Ps:** people, profit and planet
- **Sensemaking:** developing a deeper and broader understanding of the role of a company in society and how it can contribute to societal wellbeing as a for-profit organization.
- **Transformation:** transforming operational process in response to market demands and societal expectations
- **Mindset and function of manager:** finding practical ways to make these principles work

This list of preliminary principles will be analysed and further refined by a working group of academics and practitioners in a series of **workshops in spring 2023**. Stay tuned!

Resources for further use

In this section we are sharing some useful resources and materials that our participants, members and any interested stakeholders are encouraged to access and use in their business, research and teaching practices:

- Book: [The Power of AND - Responsible Business Without Trade-Offs](#), Edward Freeman, Kirsten E. Martin, and Bidhan L. Parmar, Columbia Business School Publishing, 2020
- Book: [Strategic management: A stakeholder approach](#), Edward Freeman, Pitman, 1984
- Document: [Principles of Social Value](#), Social Value, 2021
- Newspaper article: [Have the Anticapitalists Reached Harvard Business School?](#), Emma Goldberg, The New York Times, 2022
- Position paper: [Transforming business education for sustainability: the case for paradigm shifts in pedagogy and theory](#), ABIS, 2022
- Report: [Value Creation: A Dialogue on Models and Methods](#), ABIS - AMS, 2022
- Report: [Corporate Approaches to Sustainable Value Creation Report](#), ABIS - AMS, 2021

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the members of the Colloquium Steering Committee **Manuela Brusoni and Lisa Gring Pemble** for their useful insights and guidance in steering the content and goals of the event and call for papers and cases.

Lastly, the event could not have happened without our excellent speakers and all the participants! Thank you!

Business Principles for the Stakeholder Capitalism Era

29 & 30 Nov. 2022 | Hybrid

SDA Bocconi
SCHOOL OF MANAGEMENT

SOCIAL VALUE UK

Triodos Bank

OUR
CONTRIBUTING
ORGANISATIONS

Feedback

We at ABIS are thrilled that our participants and speakers enjoyed this year's theme and discussions. Here is what they shared with us!

"I have so enjoyed participating and am grateful to you for the opportunity!"

"This is an important topic! Useful framework for both business and academia"

"The research sessions were very well structured and a good choice for the presented case examples. It was great to be randomly assigned into groups during interactive sessions instead, thus fostering diversity"

"I participated in a very good panel discussion and breakout sessions"

"Thank you for welcoming me to the conference and to the ABIS community. I look forward to continuing to be involved with ABIS!"

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